

Factsheet #3

Disease Interception in neurodegenerative diseases

A CURE FOR A DISEASE YET TO COME

Imagine it would be possible to treat potentially life-threatening diseases long before the onset of the first symptoms. Disease Interception as an emerging concept in medicine, aims to do so and has been increasingly discussed, especially in regard to neurodegenerative and oncological diseases.

Advocates highlight Disease Interception as an innovative approach integrating advanced diagnostics, genetic insights, and cutting-edge technology to pinpoint risk factors and move to therapy before patients experience the first signs of their disease¹. In treating what has not materialized yet, Disease Interception could help to prevent severe illness, avoid chronic conditions, or at least prolong phases free of suffering. In addition, it might empower individuals to take preventive control of their health while reducing the burden on themselves, their families and the healthcare system.

Disease Interception is the idea of curing a disease even before the onset of the first symptoms.

What is Disease Interception?

Disease Interception is a concept that involves treating conditions before clinical symptoms manifest. Although the term has been used in the medical discourse for quite a while, no clear-cut definition exists. The term employs a metaphor of interception familiar from sports and military maneuvers.² Just as a football player or military leader gains an advantage over the situation through anticipation, Disease Interception describes a medical strategy that requires anticipat-

ing a harmful outcome (e.g. a neurodegenerative disease) that should be avoided. It then aims to interrupt the causal pathways of events to prevent the outcome from materializing (similar to the football player seeing the quarterback decide for a pass and intercepting the ball before it reaches the opponent).

Key characteristics of Disease Interception according to Narchi & Winkler²

Early detection

A disease has begun but is clinically inapparent.

High certainty

Without intervention, the disease will likely manifest fully.

Window of opportunity

There is a specific time window in which the progression can either be prevented or significantly delayed.

Individual treatment

Specific treatment options, usually pharmacological, are available.

Evolving patterns in the ethical debate

From a larger perspective, Disease Interception can be understood as part of an individual prevention paradigm that has dominated approaches to medicine and public health in the last decades.² The prevention paradigm refers to a proactive approach aimed at reducing the risks of disease and its consequences before they occur. This paradigm emphasizes early intervention strategies that target the root causes of diseases and health issues, with the goal of maintaining health and minimizing the need for more costly or invasive treatments later.

However, unlike known prevention strategies, Disease Interception expands the paradigm in a very specific way by identifying and aiming at specific

anticipated course of events towards more favorable outcomes.

The healthy, yet diseased

From an ethical perspective, Disease Interception raises complex questions, as it may redefine the boundaries of health and disease, introduce new technological and conceptual challenges, and reshape the patient experience in profound ways.

Traditionally, the concept of illness is tripartite: Disease is understood as measurable deviations from physiological norms, illness as the personal experience of symptoms, and sickness as the societal role associated with being unwell. Disease Interception focuses on identifying and addressing disease in its earliest stages before clinical symptoms appear. This challenges the conventional understanding of illness by emphasizing

Disease Interception and the case of Alzheimer's - a scenario

individuals who have not yet developed a disease and providing therapy.

This is in contrast to strategies detecting early signs of already existing disease or screening populations at risk, both usually implemented at population level. It first suggests the existence of discrete but accurate indicators of future disease, even before a prodromal stage. Second it implies a reliable causal chain between current actions and future events, creating an intervention field where the probable can be averted. Finally, it presupposes the existence of measures and treatment options to effectively change the

the biological markers of disease over subjective experiences of being unwell. Disease Interception emphasizes the detection in individuals who may feel entirely healthy, bypassing the experience of illness while still requiring the adoption of a social role someone being treated. This creates a new category of individuals who can be assigned the state of disease but not illness. These "healthy yet diseased" individuals are increasingly identified by predictive approaches such as Disease Interception, creating the paradox of the "healthy sick" who live in the tension between present well-being and anticipated illness.

Health as management of future disease

Health, on the other hand, is no longer merely the absence of symptoms but also the management of future probabilities of disease. Medical practice shifts from a reactive approach—treating illnesses after symptoms emerge—to a proactive paradigm that intervenes in, and potentially colonizes, symptom-free stages to prevent disease progression. This focus on potential future conditions blurs the boundaries between health and illness, creating a world in which predictions and anticipations of disease shape present-day medical decisions.

With Disease Interception it is suggested that health becomes a manageable condition in the future instead of a state of being in the present.

Overmedicalising the present

The inclusion of future probabilities in the concept of health risks, finally, raises concerns of overmedicalizing individuals, turning them into patients based on uncertain or probabilistic information. This shift raises concerns about autonomy and self-determination, as individuals may feel pressured to act on predictions they may not fully understand. In this evolving framework, health is no longer defined solely by the present state of the body but also by its anticipated future, prompting a re-examination of what it means to be healthy in a world of technological medicine.

Technically produced decision spaces

As these critical concerns indicate, Disease Interception introduces a profound shift in how health and illness are approached. It is often neglected in ethical considerations that Disease Interception also heavily relies on the use of technological components. As digital health technologies, artificial intelligence, and big data become integral to predicting and preventing diseases, they transform human-environment relationships by mediating perceptions aforementioned shifts. This reliance on technology not only redefines the decision-making space in healthcare, but also raises critical ethical considerations about individual agency versus technology-mediated values such as the prioritization of future health over present well-being, and the societal implications of living in a state of anticipated illness.

Ethical challenges of technologically anticipated health and illness

With this, Disease Interception introduces a significant shift in the power dynamics of medical

decision-making by reframing individuals as “anticipated patients”, who may perceive themselves as diseased despite experiencing no subjective illness. This redefinition positions healthcare experts as the primary agents in identifying risks and proposing interventions, shifting decision-making agency away from patients. In addition, advanced technologies may amplify this shift by technologically materializing a preference of future health over present well-being, creating a tension between addressing potential risks and preserving current autonomy.

The technological mediation of the process of Disease Interception, hence, risks creating epistemic vulnerabilities for patients. Unlike traditional doctor-patient interactions, where decisions are often grounded in shared understanding of present conditions, Disease Interception requires patients to navigate complex, often non-transparent technological systems, while having no access to the phenomenal experience of “being ill”. Technologies such as AI algorithms and predictive models are frequently described as “black boxes,” meaning their inner workings are inaccessible or incomprehensible to the average person. This lack of transparency and access to experience undermines patients’ ability to make informed and autonomous decisions, as they must rely on the purported authority of the technology and its interpreters.

Second, the reliance on technology can also lead to a moral vulnerability in the doctor-patient relationship. Patients may feel pressured to accept proposed interventions to avoid being held accountable for future health outcomes. The moral weight of rejecting an intervention—especially one framed as a preventive measure—can position patients as irresponsible or negligent if they later develop the predicted illness. This dynamic risks shifting the focus of responsibility onto patients, reducing the role of healthcare professionals to that of facilitators of technological recommendations rather than empathetic guides. For

Reliance on technology in disease interception can lead to moral vulnerability, when prioritizing the future is not a choice but a preference embedded in the machine.

patients, the integration of Disease Interception into healthcare introduces a uniquely challenging reality. Engaging in pre-clinical testing and diagnosis places individuals in a situation of forced choice: once a risk or pre-disease state is identified, inaction becomes a decision against treatment. Additionally, there is a danger of paternalism, where the healthcare system, driven by

the imperative to prioritize future health, may unintentionally constrain patient autonomy. This can lead to societal stigmatization, with patients who opt out of treatment being judged for not addressing their condition. Beyond these social pressures, the psychological burden of knowing one's risk of future disease can mirror the distress associated with, for example, genetic diagnoses, creating ongoing anxiety and uncertainty about one's health and future

The promise of Disease Interception, thus, comes with a range of complex ethical dilemmas that must be carefully considered as these strategies evolve. Key ethical considerations for the future of Disease Interception include patients' ability to opt out of the decision space created by Disease Interception, exercising a right to non-knowledge or non-obligation about potential risks. In addition, technology development alongside the strategic aim of Disease Interception should not be considered value-neutral but must be included in ethical considerations.

References

¹Jessen, F.; Bug, C. (Eds.) (2019): Disease Interception. Bonn: e-relations Verlag.

²Narchi, Jonas; Winkler, Eva C. (2021): Nipping Diseases in the Bud? Ethical and Social Considerations of the Concept of 'Disease Interception'. In Public Health Ethics 14 (1), pp. 100–108. DOI: 10.1093/phe/phaa036.

Recommendations for further reading

Wiese, Lara; Diehl, Anke; Huster, Stefan (Eds.) (2024): Disease Interception als Chance und Herausforderung. Eine interdisziplinäre Analyse. Nomos Verlagsgesellschaft. 1. Auflage. Baden-Baden: Nomos.

Read the full report

Haltaufderheide, Joschka; Ranisch, Robert (2024): Nicht ganz krank, nicht ganz frei? Disease Interception und die ethischen Implikationen technisch produzierter Entscheidungsräume. In Lara Wiese, Anke Diehl, Stefan Huster (Eds.): Disease Interception als Chance und Herausforderung. Eine interdisziplinäre Analyse. 1. Auflage. Baden-Baden: Nomos. pp. 93–110.

About the Digital Medical Ethics Network

Digitalization is rapidly changing the healthcare system and is having an increasing impact on practice. The use of new artificial intelligence technologies in diagnosis and therapy, mobile health applications on smartphones or the use of robotics holds a wide range of potential. However, it is also associated with ethical risks. Understanding these challenges and dealing with them is the task of medical ethics. Researchers need new knowledge and skills for this. The aim of the Digital Medical Ethics Network (DiMEN) is to support them in this task by conducting research, developing freely available resources and strengthening networks among researchers. <https://www.digitalemedicalethics.net>

About the authors

Dr. Joschka Haltaufderheide

is research associate at the Juniorprofessorship for Medical Ethics with a Focus of Digitization. He is working in the field of ethics of new bio- and health technologies and philosophy of technology.

Prof. Dr. Robert Ranisch

is Juniorprofessor for Medical Ethics with a Focus of Digitization. His research interests include fundamental questions of Medical Ethics, especially related to digitization and technologies.

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Contact us

For more Information about our activities please contact

Prof. Dr. Robert Ranisch
Juniorprofessorship for Medical Ethics
with a Focus on Digitization
Faculty of Health Sciences Brandenburg
University of Potsdam
ranisch@uni-potsdam.de

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